

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
College of Engineering and Technology

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2017-18
M.TECH IN STRUCTURAL ENGINEERING

I SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCSE11	Computational Structural Mechanics	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	17SCSE12	Advanced Design of RCC Structures	4			50	50	100	04
3	17SCSE13	Mechanics of Deformable Bodies	4			50	50	100	04
4	17SCSE14	Structural Dynamics	4			50	50	100	04
5	17SCSE15	Stability Analysis of structures	4			50	50	100	04
6	17SCSE16X	Elective I	4			50	50	100	04
7	17SCSE17	Structural Engineering Lab -1	2		2	50	50	100	02
8	17SCSE18	Seminar	2		1	50	-	50	02
		Total Marks/Credit						750	28

Elective I	
17SCSE161	Special concrete
17SCSE162	Repair and rehabilitation of structures
17SCSE163	AI& expert system in structural engineering
17SCSE164	Advanced Design of Pre-stressed Concrete
17SCSE165	Ground Improvement Techniques

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II SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCSE21	Design of Plates and Shells	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	17SCSE22	Earthquake Resistant structures	4			50	50	100	04
3	17SCSE23	Design of industrial structures	4			50	50	100	04
4	17SCSE24	Finite element method of analysis	4			50	50	100	04
5	17SCSE25X	Elective II	4			50	50	100	04
6	17SCSE26X	Elective III	4			50	50	100	04
7	17SCSE27	Structural Engineering Lab - 2	2		2	50	50	100	02
8	17SCSE28	Seminar	2		1	50	-	50	02
		Total Marks/Credit						750	28

Elective II		Elective III	
17SCSE 251	Design concepts of substructures	17SCSE 261	Design of Tall structures
17SCSE 252	Reliability analysis of structures	17SCSE 262	Design of concrete bridges
17SCSE 253	Masonry structures	17SCSE 263	Optimization techniques
17SCSE 254	Advanced Design of Steel Structures	17SCSE 264	Offshore Structural Engineering
17SCSE 255	Research Methodology	17SCSE 265	Advanced Strength of Materials

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III SEMESTER

SL. No	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCSE31	Seminar/Presentation on Internship (After 8 weeks from the date of commencement)				25	-	25	01
2	17SCSE32	Report on Internship				75	-	75	02
3	17SCSE33	Evaluation and Viva-Voce				-	125	125	06
		Total Marks/Credit						225	09

Note:

- 1. Internship:** All the students shall have to undergo mandatory internship of 16 weeks during III semester and University examination shall be conducted at the end of 16 weeks. Internship shall be considered as a head of passing and shall be considered for the award of degree. Those, who do not take-up/complete the internship shall be declared as failed and have to complete during the subsequent University examination after satisfying the internship requirements.
- 2. Seminar /Presentation of Internship:** Students in consultation with the guide/co-guide if any, shall prepare and present a seminar after 8 weeks of Internship. IA marks shall be awarded by a committee comprising of HoD as Chairman, Guide/co-guide if any, and a senior faculty of the department. The IA marks awarded for Seminar/Presentation on Internship, shall be based on the evaluation of Internship Report, Presentation skill and Question and Answer session.
- 3. Evaluation and Viva-Voce:** Students in consultation with the guide/co-guide if any, shall prepare relevant Internship report, and present a seminar at the end of 16 weeks. IA marks shall be awarded by a committee comprising of HoD as Chairman, Guide/co-guide if any, and a senior faculty of the department based on the evaluation of Internship Report, Presentation skill and Question and Answer session. Examination marks shall be awarded by External Guide and the Internal Guide/co-guide if any, based on the evaluation of Internship Report, Presentation skill and Question and Answer session.

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IV SEMESTER

SL. No	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCSE41	Project Work Phase: 1				50	-	50	01
2	17SCSE42	Report on Project work				50	-	50	03
3	17SCSE43	Final Evaluation of Project Work and Viva-Voce				-	100	100	06
		Total Marks/Credit						100	10

Note:

- 1. Project Phase-1:** Students in consultation with the guide/co-guide if any, shall pursue literature survey and complete the preliminary requirements of selected Project work. Each student shall prepare relevant introductory project document, and present a seminar. IA marks shall be awarded by a committee comprising of HoD as Chairman, Guide/co-guide if any, and a senior faculty of the department. The IA marks awarded for project work phase:1, shall be based on the evaluation of Project Report, Project Presentation skill and Question and Answer session.
- 2. Final Evaluation of Project Work and Viva-Voce:** Students in consultation with the guide/co-guide if any, shall prepare relevant project report, and present a seminar. IA marks shall be awarded by a committee comprising of HoD as Chairman, Guide/co-guide if any, and a senior faculty of the department based on the evaluation of Project Report, Project Presentation skill and Question and Answer session. Examination marks shall be awarded by External Guide and the Internal Guide/co-guide if any, based on the evaluation of Project Report, Project Presentation skill and Question and Answer session.